

Inactivation effect of ultraviolet-C (UVC) irradiation on different microorganisms: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

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Summary

Problems caused by increasing multidrug resistance and contamination sources around the world, as well as major infectious events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, affect the world on a global scale. For this reason, there is a need to investigate sterilization and disinfection methods and to develop new environmentally friendly methods with a wide range of implementation capacity. In this study, the effect of ultraviolet-C (UVC) irradiation on different microorganisms was investigated with different application times. In addition, observations were made about the presence of reactivation in microorganisms with dark and light applications. *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were selected as test organisms for in vitro experimental studies. When all results were evaluated, it was found

that *E.coli* was most affected by UVC among microorganisms. A direct ratio was determined between application duration and the lethal effect. These results provide information about time required for UVC application, which is an environmentally friendly method for killing these microorganisms responsible for major infections. In addition, the reactivation properties of microorganisms were also examined with varying results. It was determined that the number of reactivated microorganisms were high in the light application compared to the dark application, but for some microorganisms, the reactivation was high at dark application.

Key words

Ultraviolet light, UVC, *Staphylococcus aureus*,
Bacillus cereus, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

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Introduction

Increasing worldwide use of antibiotics against infectious diseases resulted in parallel in significant side-effects. The most important of these problems is the increase of multi-drug resistant microorganisms and the fact that these microorganisms cause serious infectious diseases. Due to increasing drug resistance problems, many have expressed their concern that the absence of drastic antibacterials will regress the infectious diseases field to the past, leading to uncontrollable infection rise. In addition, the fact that antibiotics are used continuously in animal farms and aquaculture, besides their use in hospitals and community settings, reveals the magnitude of this risk. To prevent these situations, the World Health Organization (WHO) and related institutions should take action to focus on alternative prevention and control practices for infectious diseases, including resistant and outbreaks strains. Bush et al¹ emphasized that to prevent infectious diseases and drug resistance, new generation approaches should be introduced and such research should be encouraged by international health organizations.

With the increase in health awareness, the interest

in natural products with antibacterial, antifungal and antiviral activities is increasing day by day.² Among these products, the active compounds of the plants predominate, while another important option is ultraviolet (UV) applications. The earliest observations of the germicidal effects of UV radiation belong to Downes and Blunt,³ who reported that sunlight inactivates bacteria and found the blue-violet spectrum to be the most effective spectrum. Studies showing the lethal effect of sunlight on microorganisms such as *Bacillus anthracis*, *Tyrothrix scaber*, *Bacillus typhosus* date back to the 19th century.^{4,5} It was reported that the first use of UV for the purpose of killing microorganisms and disinfecting was on the disinfection of drinking water.^{6,7} Further studies demonstrated the lethal effects of UV irradiation on fungi and viruses.^{8,9,10,11,12}

Light sources such as UV have many advantages over other anti-microbial disinfectants. Some of these advantages can be listed as follows; It is environmentally friendly and non-polluting, does not cause much harm to the surrounding materials – be it organic-inorganic or different living biological agents, it is relatively more economical than other techniques. One of the important features of these techniques, which

have many more advantages, is that they take effect in a very short time.¹³

UV is electromagnetic radiation which has a wavelength shorter than visible light (400-700 nm) and longer than X-rays (<100 nm) in the range of 100 to 400 nm. UV radiation is mainly studied in four different spectral fields including vacuum UV (VUV) (100–200 nm), UVC (200–280 nm), UVB (280–315 nm) and UVA (315–400 nm).^{12,14} UVA is divided into two as UVA1 (340–400 nm) and UVA2 (320–340 nm).^{15,16}

Between 1970 and 1987, a significant amount of UV radiation reached the earth's surface due to the damage to the ozone layer. There is no natural exposure to UVC as the stratospheric ozone layer blocks wavelengths less than 290 nm. UVB penetrates into the ozone layer and accounts for 5-10% of terrestrial solar UV radiation. More than 90% of the solar radiation reaching the earth's surface is UVA.^{17,18}

UVA possesses the lowest energy and is thus the least dangerous UV light component. It is not considered to be germicidal. UVA rays cause discoloration of the skin, which is described as tanning. Therefore, it is used in tanning beds.^{19,20}

VUV are the most energetic wavelengths in the UV spectrum. It interacts easily with oxygen atoms and its interactions with organic molecules are harmful even at low doses. Owing to their high energy, they exist only in a vacuum.²¹

UVB causes sunburn on the skin and is known to be associated with photocarcinogenesis and photoaging.¹³ It is widely recognized as the main cause of skin cancer related to sunburn, redness, and skin tanning.^{14,22} When human skin is exposed to UVB, it is absorbed by keratinocyte DNA.^{16,23} On the other hand, its wavelength is responsible for vitamin D synthesis.^{21,24}

UVC covers wavelengths between 200 and 280 nm, and this spectrum is also called "germicidal" due to its biocidal effects on bacteria.^{20,25} Its lethal effect on microorganisms is due to damage of the genetic material in the nucleus of the cell or the nucleic acids in the virus.^{14,26} This damage is defined by the inactivation of DNA and RNA, which occurs with the formation of pyrimidine dimers from thymine and cytosine.^{27,28,29} This dimers formation inhibits normal replication, causing inactivation of microorganisms. On the other hand, many microorganisms have the ability to repair DNA damage by light-independent (dark repair) or light-dependent (photoreactivation) mechanisms. Photoreactivation can be defined as the recovery of activity by the photolyase enzyme of inactivated microorganisms by repairing pyrimidine dimers in DNA under light. Another repair is the excision repair, known as the dark repair.^{30,31,32,33} Although photoreac-

tivation and dark repair reduce the effectiveness of UV inactivation, UVC light absorbed by nucleic acids and proteins is used in many applications, including water purification, air and laboratory disinfection, sterilization of medical products, preservation of food and beverages.²¹ The disinfection effect may vary depending on the distance to the UVC source, the application time and the microorganism density.³⁴ Similarly, the photoreactivation and dark repair abilities of organisms also vary considerably from species to species.

In this study, the inactivation effects of UVC on different microorganisms were evaluated with different application times. In order to comment on the presence of dark repair and photoreactivation, the incubations of microorganisms in light and dark conditions after UVC application were examined. Since the UVC effect varies according to microorganisms and application times, data of 8 different exposure times were evaluated.

Materials and Methods

Microorganisms

Staphylococcus aureus, *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were selected as test organisms in the study. These microorganisms are hospital-acquired clinical isolates that we isolated in our previous studies and were obtained from the laboratory of Bozkurt Biotechnology R&D Services Industry and Trade Limited Company. Bacterial strains were inoculated into 250 mL Erlenmeyer containing 100 mL of Nutrient Broth (Merck, Germany). Bacterial strains were incubated in orbital shaker at 100 rpm and 37°. They were kept in incubation for 16-24 hours until reaching a bacterial growth density corresponding to 0.5 McFarland standard turbidity (1-2 x 10⁸ colony forming units (CFU/mL).

Media was poured into sterile Petri dishes before planting bacteria. Nutrient Agar (Merck, Germany) powder was weighed in the amount recommended by the trademark and mixed in an Erlenmeyer containing 1 l of distilled water. The mixture was sterilized in an autoclave. After sterilization, the mixture was left to cool and after reaching the appropriate temperature, it was poured into plastic Petri plates. A few of the Petri dishes containing the nutrient medium were kept in the incubator and checked for contamination.

For each experimental study, 0.1 mL of bacterial cultures with 0.5 McFarland density were taken and spread over the surfaces of Petri dishes with 9 cm diameter by spreading plate method and then they were incubated at 37°.

UVC Applications

After the Petri dishes were planted, they were immediately placed at a distance of 24 cm from the UVC light source (Philips UV-C TUV PL-L 36W / 4P). Petri dishes were exposed to UVC light source for different durations (10s, 20s, 30s, 45s, 1 min, 2 min, 4 min, 10 min) at room temperature (20-22°).

After UVC application, the Petri dishes were incubated in dark and light conditions. Petri dishes were covered with aluminum foil to ensure dark conditions. It is aimed to prevent light repair in microorganisms kept in the dark and to prevent dark repair in microorganisms kept in the light. For the light application microorganisms were incubated under white light.

In order to measure the average radiation exposure of microorganisms, Delta Ohm brand HD 2102.1 model radiation meter (Caselle di Selvazzano, Italy) supplemented with LP 471 UVC probe was used.

Counting Bacteria

Colonies developing in the Petri dishes after 24 hours of incubation were counted and Petri dishes were observed for up to 48 hours to see if growth would occur. Counts were made through plain vision as colonies can be seen easily with the naked eye (Figure 1). Counted colonies were calculated as colony forming units per milliliter (CFU/mL) and log CFU reduction was calculated for each case. Log CFU reduction values are given in parentheses throughout the article.

Statistical Analysis

All trials were set up in a randomized plot design with three replications. The obtained data were analyzed using JMP 8 (SAS Institute Inc., Raleigh, NC, USA) statistical program and variance analysis was performed. The differences between them were compared with the LSD multiple comparison test.

The in vitro lethal effects of UVC on different microorganisms were tested under different application conditions with different durations. Obtained values were compared according to microorganisms and application conditions.

Result and Discussion

In the trials of the effectiveness of UVC on microorganisms, all studies were carried out using a Philips brand UVC lamp. In the measurement made with the radiation meter, the UVC density to which the microorganisms were exposed was found to be 1.5 mW/cm².

Colonies that developed after UVC exposure were meticulously counted and evaluated in detail (Figure 2).

According to statistical analysis results, the strain most affected by UVC among microorganisms was *E.coli* (25.31 CFU/mL, log 5.59). Although there is no statistically significant difference between other microorganisms, the most affected are *K. pneumoniae* (40.56

Figure 1

Counting of *E.coli* colonies incubated in bright culture conditions. (a) non-UVC treated control plate, (b) 30-sec UVC-treated plate, (c) 1 min UVC-treated plate, (d) 2 min UVC-treated plate, (e) 4 min UVC-treated plate, (f) 10 min UVC treated plate.

Figure 2

Microorganisms were incubated in dark culture conditions after 30-sec UVC exposure. (a) *B.cereus*, (b) *K. pneumoniae*, (c) *E.coli*, (d) *S.aureus*.

CFU/mL, log 5.39), *S. Aureus* (45.64 CFU/mL, log 5.34), and *B. cereus* (46.79 CFU/mL, log 5.32), respectively.

Considering the application times of UVC, the expected results were obtained. According to these results, it was determined that the most effective application time was 10 minutes (0.12 CFU/mL, log 7.90) and 4 minutes (0.12 CFU/mL, log 7.90). This is followed by administration times of 2 min (2.87 CFU/mL, log 6.54) and 1 min (5 CFU/mL, log 6.30), respectively, and statistically significant differences were not detected. Although the most effective application times are the 4 different times mentioned above, it has been determined that other application times such as 45s (17.95 CFU/mL, log 5.74), 30s (19.50 CFU/mL, log 5.70), 20s (30 CFU/mL, log 5.52), and 10s (241.04 CFU/mL, log 4.61) also have lethal effects on microorganisms. In addition to these, a trial was set up for an application time of 5 seconds. However, it was not taken into consideration because there was an uncountable amount of bacterial growth.

Regarding the effect of dark and light conditions on UV exposure or the presence of a repair mechanism, it was determined that the light (47.57 CFU/mL, log 5.32) application provides more microorganisms reactivations than the dark application (31.58 CFU/mL, log 5.50).

When the microorganisms and the application conditions were evaluated together, the highest number of microorganisms was detected in *S.aureus* (78.79 CFU/mL, log 5.10) in the light application. The lowest number was detected in *S.aureus* (12.50 CFU/mL, log 5.90) in the dark application.

When the application times and bacterial strains

are evaluated together, it was observed that the 10-minute application period had an inactivating effect on *E.coli* (0 CFU/mL, log 8), *B.cereus* (0 CFU/mL, log 8), and *S.aureus* (0 CFU/mL, log 8), the 4-minute application period had an inactivating effect on *B.cereus* (0 CFU/mL, log 8), *K.pneumoniae* (0 CFU/mL, log 8) and *S.aureus* (0 CFU/mL, log 8), the 2 minutes application period had an inactivating effect on *K.pneumoniae* (0 CFU/mL, log 8), but there was no statistical difference among them. Again, although there were no statistical differences, it was determined that 10 minutes of application time had an inactivating effect on *K. pneumoniae* (0.5 CFU/mL, log 7.30), 4 minutes of application time had an inactivating effect on *E. coli* (0.5 CFU/mL, log 7.30), 2 minutes of application time had an inactivating effect on *B.cereus* (0,5 CFU/mL, log 7.30) and *S.aureus* (0,5 CFU/mL, log 7.30), 1 minute of application time had an inactivating effect on *S.aureus* (0.5 CFU/mL, log 7.30). The lowest inactivation effect was detected in *S.aureus* (321.66 CFU/mL, log 4.49), *B.cereus* (302.5 CFU/mL, log 4.51), and *K. pneumoniae* (265 CFU/mL, log 4.57) in 10 seconds of application.

When all factors were evaluated at the same time, the highest number of microorganisms was detected in the *S.aureus* (583,33 CFU/mL, log 4.23) strain, which was exposed to for 10 seconds UVC and incubated in light conditions. During the same application time, the highest colony (550 CFU/mL, log 4.25) was detected in *B.cereus* under dark culture conditions, and this was followed by with 10 sec application time *K. pneumoniae* (500 CFU/mL, log 4.30) under the light condition and *E.coli* (85 CFU/mL, log 5.07) under the dark condition. It was determined that a shorter appli-

cation time is also effective on bacterial strains under different culture conditions. For example, while 1 CFU/mL (log 7) colony was detected in *S.aureus* under 1 min application time and dark culture conditions, no colonies were detected in *S.aureus* under 1 min application time and light culture conditions (Table 1).

It has been confirmed in this study that as the UVC irradiation time increases, the inactivation effect on microorganisms also increases and differs among strains. In a similar study,³⁵ it was emphasized that there is a direct correlation between the increase in irradiation dose and the level of inactivation on microorganisms. In addition, different UV sensitivities were reported in gram-positive bacteria, gram-negative bacteria, and yeasts.

In a different study,³⁶ researchers examined the effects of UV radiation on MRSA (methicillin-resistant *S.aureus*) and multidrug-resistant *A.baumannii*. It has

been determined that 10 seconds of application has an inhibition effect of 25% in MRSA and 10% in *A.baumannii* and that 15-second application has an inhibition effect of 67% in MRSA and 70% in *A.baumannii*. They found that as the application time (20, 25, 30, and 35 seconds) increased, it had an effect up to 96-98%. When their studies are examined, it is seen that even very short-term UV exposure has significant effects on bacteria. Although it is very difficult to compare our results with these studies because detailed information about the UV source could not be obtained, in our study, a high lethal effect was detected in UVC exposure for 20 seconds and longer exposures.

UVC and similar light emitting systems have a wide range of uses from food to health areas, and have been researched for their anti-infective or sterilizing properties. As an example, in a study,³⁷ the effects of UVC, near-infrared (NIR), and UVC-NIR on microbial in-

Table 1 Effects of UVC on different microorganisms under different application times and conditions.

	<i>S.aureus</i>		<i>B.cereus</i>		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	
	Light	Dark	Light	Dark	Light	Dark	Light	Dark
10 sec	583,33 A (log 4.23)	60 DEF (log 5.22)	55 EFG (log 5.25)	550 B (log 4.25)	65 DE (log 5.18)	85 D (log 5.07)	500 C (log 4.30)	30 GHIJK (log 5.52)
20 sec	10 HIJKL (log 6)	23 HIJKL (log 5.63)	36 FGH (log 5.44)	25 HIJKL (log 5.60)	66 DE (log 5.18)	25 HIJKL (log 5.60)	20 HIJKL (log 5.69)	35 FGHI (log 5.45)
30 sec	18 HIJKL (log 5.74)	9 HIJKL (log 6.04)	7 IJKL (log 6.15)	14 HIJKL (log 5.85)	28 GHIJKL (log 5.55)	35 FGHI (log 5.45)	15 HIJKL (log 5.82)	30 GHIJK (log 5.52)
45 sec	18 HIJKL (log 5.74)	6 JKL (log 6.22)	28 GHIJKL (log 5.55)	14,66 HIJKL (log 5.83)	33 GHIJ (log 5.48)	30 GHIJK (log 5.52)	5 JKL (log 6.30)	9 HIJKL (log 6.04)
1 min	0 L (log 8)	1 L (log 7)	8 HIJKL (log 6.09)	10 HIJKL (log 6)	10 HIJKL (log 6)	7 IJKL (log 6.15)	0 L (log 8)	4 KL (log 6.39)
2 min	1 L (log 7)	1 L (log 7)	0 L (log 8)	1 L (log 7)	15 HIJKL (log 5.82)	5 JKL (log 6.30)	0 L (log 8)	0 L (log 8)
4 min	0 L (log 8)	0 L (log 8)	0 L (log 8)	0 L (log 8)	1 L (log 7)	0 L (log 8)	0 L (log 8)	0 L (log 8)
10 min	0 L (log 8)	0 L (log 8)	0 L (log 8)	0 L (log 8)	0 L (log 8)	0 L (log 8)	0 L (log 8)	1 L (log 7)

P<0,05*, P<0,01**, P<0,001***, LSD value was calculated according to the angle conversion value. Different letters (A–L) indicate significant differences according to the LSD test (p ≤ 0.05). LSD strain: 8,25***, LSD time: 11,67***, LSD condition: 5,83***, LSD strain*time: 23,34***, LSD strain*condition: 11,67***, LSD time*condition: 16,50***, LSD strain*time*condition: 33,01***.

activation were investigated on *E. coli* and *S. typhimurium* inoculated on the powdered red pepper. Reducing effects of UVC at the rate of 0.03 log, of NIR at the rate of 1.45 log and of UVC-NIR at the rate of 3.34 log were determined on *S. typhimurium* in 5 minutes of application time. On *E. coli*, researchers demonstrated that UVC had a reducing effect of 0.04 log, NIR at a rate of 1.42 log, and UVC-NIR at a rate of 2.78 log. It was also emphasized that co-administration had a synergistic effect.

In the experimental studies conducted within the scope of this research, it was observed that UVC applications showed different inactivation effects compared to bacterial strains, while light or dark repair mechanisms also showed differences.

In a study examining the regrowth potential of bacteria after UV disinfection in the absence of light and dark repair, researchers³⁸ reported that the regrowth percentages of *E. coli* and bacteria in wastewater differed. Accordingly, they reported that 40 mJ/cm² application was higher than 15 mJ/cm² in regrowth percentage.

Oguma et al.³² investigated the mechanisms of UV inactivation, photorepair, and dark repair of *E. coli* and *C. parvum* with the endonuclease sensitive site (ESS) test. Regarding *E. coli*, a high inactivation correlation was observed between the dose of UV irradiation and the number of pyrimidine dimers induced in the DNA of *E. coli*. In addition, it was determined that the colony-forming ability of *E. coli* was highly correlated with the number of pyrimidine dimers in DNA. It was found that when *E. coli* was exposed to fluorescent light after UV inactivation, UV-induced pyrimidine dimers in DNA were continuously repaired and colony-forming ability

was gradually restored. In the dark, they did not encounter such a result. In a similar study,³⁹ it was emphasized that reactivation after UV application occurred to a lesser extent in dark repair than in photoreactivation. In the study in this article, although it was concluded that light was effective in reactivation, it was observed that dark application could provide visible repair in some bacteria, like in *B. cereus*.

Conclusion

The increase of drug-resistant microorganisms, the threat of epidemics to life, and the emergence of pandemics such as COVID-19 have built an unfavorable infectious surrounding. Among the practices aiming at minimizing the burden of this surrounding, UVC is an important environmentally friendly option. This article focused on the lethal effect of UVC on different microorganisms and examined the effect of dark and light on reactivation. The results of the study confirm that the lethal effect also increases with the increase in the application time of UVC. Considering the light and dark applications, it was concluded that the reactivation in the dark occurred less often than photoreactivation. However, it was observed that reactivation may vary depending on microorganism's species, as well as, the UVC doses of exposure.

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Περίληψη

Inactivation effect of ultraviolet-C (UVC) irradiation on different microorganisms: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

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Τα προβλήματα που προκαλούνται από την αυξανόμενη αντοχή σε πολλά φάρμακα, καθώς και η εμφάνιση μολυσματικών παραγόντων, ειδικά με τη μορφή επιδημιών, όπως η πανδημία COVID-19, επηρεάζουν όλο τον κόσμο σε παγκόσμια κλίμακα. Για το λόγο αυτό, υπάρχει ανάγκη να διερευνηθούν μέθοδοι αποστείρωσης και απολύμανσης και να αναπτυχθούν νέες φιλικές προς το περιβάλλον μέθοδοι με εκτεταμένο φάσμα δράσης. Στην παρούσα μελέτη διερευνήθηκε η επίδραση της υπεριώδους ακτινοβολίας-C (UVC) σε διαφορετικούς μικροοργανισμούς με διαφορετικούς χρόνους εφαρμογής. Επιπλέον, έγιναν παρατηρήσεις για την παρουσία επανενεργοποίησης σε μικροοργανισμούς με εφαρμογές φωτός και σκότους. Τα βακτήρια *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* επιλέχθηκαν ως μικροοργανισμοί για τις in vitro πειραματικές μελέτες. Σύμφωνα με τα αποτελέσματα της μελέτης, το βακτήριο *E. coli* φάνηκε να επηρεάστηκε περισσότερο από την UVC μεταξύ των υπό έλεγχο μικροοργανισμών. Προσδιορίστηκε μια άμεση αναλογία μεταξύ των χρόνων εφαρμογής και του θανατηφόρου αποτελέσματος. Αυτά τα αποτελέσματα παρέχουν πληροφορίες σχετικά με τον χρόνο που απαιτείται για την εφαρμογή UVC, η οποία είναι μια φιλική προς το περιβάλλον μέθοδος για τη θανάτωση αυτών των μικροοργανισμών που ευθύνονται για σοβαρές λοιμώξεις. Επιπλέον, εξετάστηκαν και οι ιδιότητες επανενεργοποίησης των μικροοργανισμών. Διαπιστώθηκε ότι ο αριθμός των επανενεργοποιημένων μικροοργανισμών ήταν υψηλός στην εφαρμογή με φως σε σύγκριση με την εφαρμογή σκότους, ενώ σε ορισμένους μικροοργανισμούς, η επανενεργοποίηση ήταν υψηλή κατά την εφαρμογή σκότους.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

υπεριώδες φως, UVC, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

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